

1 **Immunoglobulin rearrangement events are associated with disease progression in human breast**
2 **cancer.**

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7 We describe here data indicating rearrangement of immunoglobulin gene segments is a fundamental
8 transcriptional feature of disease progression. Immunoglobulin gene rearrangement was a central feature
9 of metastasis to the lymph nodes in humans with breast cancer, considered a central aspect of disease
10 progression. When comparing the primary tumors of breast cancer patients who do or do not have lymph
11 node metastasis, immunoglobulin gene rearrangement was already observable in the primary tumor,
12 significantly higher in patients who do have lymph node metastasis and among the largest differences
13 transcriptome-wide when comparing the primary tumors of breast cancer patients with or without lymph
14 node metastasis. We are interested in evaluating whether these rearrangement events can be utilized as
15 a surrogate of disease progression in humans with breast cancer, and in other solid tumors.
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